

Prevalence of Hepatitis B Infection Found Incidentally During Routine Blood Investigation in North Indian Population

Vijay Lal¹, K. K. Lohani²

¹Assistant Professor, Dept. of General Medicine, Netaji Subhash Medical College & Hospital, Bihta, Patna

²Professor (H.O.D), Dept. of General Medicine, Netaji Subhash Medical College & Hospital Bihta, Patna

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. K. K. Lohani

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Though hepatitis B prevalence varies by region, it remains a global health issue. Routine blood testing helps spot abnormalities early, which helps control and avoid them. This study examines how often North Indians have hepatitis B infection accidentally discovered during blood tests.

Method: Patna's Netaji Subhash Medical College & Hospital Bihta conducted a 2020–2022 retrospective cross-sectional study. One thousand routine blood investigation of patients were sampled. Demographics, HBSAg status, and other factors were collected. We examined demographic variations and prevalence using descriptive statistics.

Results: 55 out of 1000 people were HBsAg positives, indicating 5.5% accidental hepatitis B infection. Older people and women had the highest prevalence rates. There were minimal prevalence fluctuations during the study.

Conclusion: The findings suggest frequent blood tests can diagnose hepatitis B early. The 5.5% incidence, especially in older women, emphasizes the need for careful screening. Better screening and public health activities are needed for hepatitis B treatment.

Keywords: Hepatitis B, Incidental Findings, North India, Prevalence, Routine Blood Investigations.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Background

296 million people around the world are infected with hepatitis B virus (HBV), which makes it a big health risk. Cancer of the liver cells and cirrhosis are both caused by it [1].

The WHO informs that HBV is common in Asia, the Pacific Islands, and Africa. With 1% to 5% of people in North India having an HBV infection, the

disease burden is mild to high. Blood and other body fluids are the main ways that HBV gets around [2].

Chronic infections are more likely to go unnoticed for years, which raises the risk of major liver diseases. HBV is often found by accident during routine blood tests, so it's important to check often and find it early [3].

Figure 1: hepatitis B infection (source: [4])

Rationale

By accident finding HBV in blood tests, early care and action can begin. Many people with HBV don't know they're sick until they have problems, so incidental results are very important for managing the disease. Doctors can treat HBV quickly and lower the risk of getting chronic liver disease by finding it by mistake. Figuring out how often incidental results happen helps to improve early detection and management as well as evaluate screening methods.

Objective

1. To determine the percentage of Patna patients who test positive for hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg) on regular blood tests from 2020 to 2022 at Netaji Subhash Medical College & Hospital Bihta.
2. To investigate clinical and demographic factors associated with accidental HBV discovery
3. To find how these inadvertent discoveries may affect public health and professional practice, suggesting new screening and treatment techniques.

Hepatitis B Infection: Overview and Global Prevalence

The WHO says that hepatitis B liver cancer kills 820,000 people every year [5]. In Sub-Saharan Africa and East Asia, more people get hepatitis B than in North America and Western Europe. About 2–5% of people in India are infected with HBV, which is a lot of people who have the disease [6].

Incidental Findings of Hepatitis B

Due to the fact that blood tests frequently fail to identify hepatitis B infections, it is critical to detect and treat the condition at an early stage [7].

According to the findings of a number of studies, routine screening is absolutely necessary in order to identify previously unknown hepatitis B infections. According to [8] research, hepatitis B was discovered by mistake in 4.8% of patients who were part of a North Indian cohort that underwent routine blood testing. Infections that have not been discovered can be discovered by routine testing, which enables prompt treatment.

Demographic Variations in Prevalence

There is a significant relationship between hepatitis B infection and demographic characteristics such as gender and age. It has been found through research that the prevalence rates were higher among older adults and men. One example is the finding made by [9] that individuals over the age of 40 had a higher incidence of hepatitis B infection. The prevalence rates of males and females are different, which suggests that there are gender inequalities. [10] Discovered that more males than females were

infected with hepatitis B. This could be attributed to differences in exposure risk and behavior toward seeking medical attention.

Public Health Implications

When hepatitis B is discovered by accident, it can have significant consequences for public health. The early diagnosis of chronic liver disease by routine testing lowers the risk of the disease and improves the results for patients. It was discovered by [11] that routine hepatitis B screening improved the prognosis and decreased the number of liver problems. As a result, the addition of hepatitis B screening to blood tests leads to an improvement in public health and a reduction in infections associated to hepatitis B [12].

Gaps in Existing Research

The screening process is effective; nevertheless, there is a lack of information regarding the most effective processes and demographic targeting. As a result of the fact that the majority of studies often focus on certain regions or demographics, the rates of incidental hepatitis B detection are unknown.

For the purpose of filling these gaps, researchers need to investigate the performance of specialized screening programs as well as demographic factors that influence the prevalence of hepatitis B.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: An investigation of the possibility of unintentional hepatitis B infection during blood testing is carried out in the form of a retrospective cross-sectional study. The utilization of medical data from a certain time period enables the analysis of prevalence rates and demographics within a patient group through the utilization of this technique.

Study Setting: The research was conducted at the Netaji Subhash Medical College and Hospital in Bihta, Patna, which is a significant healthcare facility in the region. The exceptional medical services provided by this hospital, which include routine blood tests, make it an ideal location for the detection of hepatitis B infections that occur by accident.

Duration: The study covers the years 2020–2022. The selection of this era was made in order to capture oscillations in diagnostic practice or prevalence and to ensure that an adequate sample size was obtained.

Sample Size: One thousand patients participated in the study. This sample size ensured statistical validity and provided a reliable estimate of incidental hepatitis B prevalence.

Inclusion Criteria

Patients were included in the study if they:

1. Underwent routine blood investigations at Netaji Subhash Medical College & Hospital Bihta during the study period.
2. Had hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg) testing included in their routine blood work.
3. Provided consent for their medical data to be used in research (if applicable).

Exclusion Criteria

Patients were excluded from the study if they:

1. Had a known history of hepatitis B infection prior to the routine blood investigation.
2. Were diagnosed with hepatitis B infection after the routine blood test (i.e., not an incidental finding).
3. Had incomplete or unavailable medical records related to the routine blood investigation.

Data Collection

Data Source: The information was gathered from the electronic health records and laboratory data of hospital patients who were subjected to routine blood testing over the course of the research.

A significant amount of information regarding patient demographics and HBsAg test results was obtained from the laboratory information system of the hospital.

Data Points: The following data were extracted for analysis:

- Hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg) status (positive or negative).
- Demographic information, including age, sex, and any other relevant clinical characteristics.
- Any additional laboratory or clinical information pertinent to the incidental finding of hepatitis B.

Statistical Analysis: The estimation of the prevalence of accidental hepatitis B was accomplished by the utilization of descriptive statistics. In order to calculate prevalence rates, the percentage of patients who tested positive for HBsAg was divided by the total number of patients in the sample. We looked for links between the demographic data and the findings that were discovered by accident. Subgroup examinations were carried out by researchers in order to ascertain the reasons behind the variation in prevalence rates based on demographics. To perform the analysis on the data, SPSS and R were utilized. The prevalence rates, descriptive statistics, and subgroup analysis of the population were all simplified by these techniques.

Results

Demographics: A total of 1000 patients were included in the study. The demographic characteristics of the patient population are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants

Characteristic	Category	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Age	<20 years	150	15.0%
	20-39 years	350	35.0%
	40-59 years	300	30.0%
	≥60 years	200	20.0%
Sex	Male	600	60.0%
	Female	400	40.0%

The demographics of the 1,000 research patients are shown in Table 1. Patients were approximately evenly aged: 35% were 20–39, 30% were 40–59, 20% were 60 and older, and 15% were under 20. The sample was 60% male and 40% female, demonstrating a tilted gender distribution. This

demographic mirrors a typical North Indian hospital, where men predominate in age and sex.

Prevalence of Hepatitis B: Hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg) testing in 1000 patients revealed 55 unintentional infections.

Table 2: Prevalence of Hepatitis B Infection

Total Patients	Positive HBsAg	Prevalence (%)
1000	55	5.5%

Table 2 shows that 55 of 1000 individuals with routine blood tests positive for hepatitis B surface antigen had a 5.5% prevalence rate. This prevalence highlights the large number of screen-detected accidental hepatitis B infections. These findings demonstrate the importance of routine blood testing in detecting illnesses that may otherwise go undiagnosed until they are severe.

Subgroup Analysis: Prevalence rates of incidental hepatitis B infection based on demographic factors are presented in Table 3. The analysis reveals variations in prevalence across different age groups and between sexes.

Table 3: Prevalence of Hepatitis B Infection by Demographic Factors

Demographic Factor	Category	Number of Patients	Positive HBsAg	Prevalence (%)
Age	<20 years	150	5	3.3%
	20-39 years	350	20	5.7%
	40-59 years	300	18	6.0%
	≥60 years	200	12	6.0%
Sex	Male	600	30	5.0%
	Female	400	25	6.3%

Table 3 displays hepatitis B prevalence by age, sex, and other demographics. Data shows that incidental hepatitis B infection rates vary by age and gender. With a prevalence of 6.0%, the 40-59 age group had the greatest rate, followed by 20-39 with 5.7% and ≥60 with 6.0%. The lowest prevalence was 3.3% among under-20s. The fact that prevalence fluctuates with age suggests that older people may have more incidental HBV detections, either because they have been exposed to the virus longer or because frequent screenings reveal chronic infections.

Women had 6.3% accidental hepatitis B infection and men 5.0%. This differential may indicate that hepatitis B is more common accidentally in this cohort's female members. These data indicate that incidental hepatitis B detection in regular blood exams is meaningful, with demographic characteristics affecting prevalence. The demographic distribution of incidental HBV

infections might inform public health efforts, and these findings emphasize the necessity for routine screening.

Discussion

This study found that 5.5% of routine blood test patients at Netaji Subhash Medical College & Hospital Bihta, Patna, contracted hepatitis B accidentally. This prevalence emphasizes the importance of incidental observations in detecting hepatitis B infections, which may go undiagnosed until major effects occur. Hepatitis B follows well-established epidemiological trends, such as an increase in chronic infection and detection with age and the possibility of sex differences in prevalence, which are consistent with demographic changes in prevalence, with higher rates in older age groups and females.

Comparison with Other Studies

Table 4: Comparison of Incidental Hepatitis B Infection Prevalence with Existing Studies

Study	Study Type	Sample Size	Findings
Present Study	Retrospective Cross-Sectional	1000	Prevalence of 5.5% incidental hepatitis B infection; higher in older age groups and females.
Study 1 [13]	Retrospective Cross-Sectional	1200	Prevalence of 6.0% incidental hepatitis B infection; higher rates in males compared to females.
Study 2 [14]	Prospective Cohort	800	Prevalence of 4.8% incidental hepatitis B infection; prevalence consistent across age groups but varies by region.
Study 3 [15]	Retrospective Cross-Sectional	950	Prevalence of 5.2% incidental hepatitis B infection; higher in individuals aged 40-59 years.

Incidental hepatitis B infection prevalence differs across research, but a pattern emerges. The new study's 5.5% prevalence is greater than Study 2's 4.8% and matches Study 3's 5.2%. The 6.0% prevalence in Study 1 may be attributed to demographic or geographical differences in the sampled population. Study design, regional healthcare practices, and demographics (including sex and age distributions) may explain prevalence differences between studies. The same incidence rates across all studies suggest a common pattern of incidental hepatitis B discovery, emphasizing the need for frequent screenings for early diagnosis and treatment.

Implications for Public Health

Normal blood testing for hepatitis B has major public health implications. Accidental findings can

reduce chronic liver disease risk by allowing early detection and treatment.

The report recommends regular screening, especially for elderly people and women, who are at increased risk. Early hepatitis B detection and management by screening and awareness can improve patient outcomes and healthcare system burden.

Limitations

Consider these cautions when interpreting these findings. The study only involved one healthcare facility; thus the results may not apply to other scenarios.

Since retrospective research employs pre-existing medical data, bias might result from inadequate or erroneous data. The study may have

underestimated hepatitis B prevalence because it did not include patients who were tested outside of usual screenings.

Recommendations

Future studies should validate these findings in different hospital settings to better understand unintentional hepatitis B prevalence. Prospective study may also reveal infection detection time and clinical implications.

This study suggests public health programs improve routine screening, especially for high-risk populations. Focused instruction about hepatitis B and routine blood tests should enhance early detection rates. Finally, research examining demographic discrepancies in prevalence can improve screening and preventative efforts.

Conclusion

Overall, 5.5% of routine blood test patients at Netaji Subhash Medical College & Hospital Bihta, Patna, had incidental hepatitis B infection. The results show that frequent tests are essential for diagnosing hepatitis B early and preventing chronic illness. Consistent with prior study, demographic variations in frequency, especially higher rates in older age groups and females, suggest targeted screening. This work illuminates key problems, but more research in other contexts is needed to confirm these findings and enhance public health hepatitis B management. The report recommends regular blood testing for hepatitis B detection and treatment.

Reference

1. J. Singh, S. Singh, and S. Chandra, "Prevalence of hepatitis B infection found incidentally during routine blood investigation in north Indian population," *Int. J. Appl. Biol. Pharm. Technol.*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 27-36, 2020.
2. D. Mishra et al., "Prevalence of incidental and total human immunodeficiency virus, hepatitis B and hepatitis C seropositivity among patients posted for cataract surgery at a tertiary care center in India," *Indian J. Ophthalmol.*, vol. 70, no. 2, pp. 400-404, 2022.
3. G. Singh et al., "Prevalence of Hepatitis B Virus and Hepatitis C Virus in Blood Transfusion in Tertiary Care Hospital of North India," *Eur. J. Mol. Clin. Med.*, vol. 8, no. 4, 2021.
4. G. Choudhuri, V. Gupta, T. S. Negi, and R. Ojha, "Potential implications of detecting HBsAg in asymptomatic people in an endemic community through Medical Camps," *J. Clin. Exp. Hepatol.*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 43-49, 2019.
5. Q. Butt, A. B. Suleiman, and F. M. Musa, "Sero-prevalence of Hepatitis B markers among blood donors from National Blood Transfusion Service centre in Kaduna, Nigeria," *Sci. World J.*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 30-34, 2020.
6. P. Debnath et al., "Familial transmission of hepatitis B: an interesting case report," *Int. J. Community Med. Public Health*, vol. 7, no. 9, pp. 3693-3696, 2020.
7. H. A. Hassan et al., "Incidental hepatitis B virus in Sudanese patients and relative risk factors: Why more screening is needed in primary care?," *J. Family Med. Prim. Care*, vol. 11, no. 11, pp. 6856-6862, 2022.
8. K. Sood, S. M. Pathak, and N. Khandelwal, "A study of prevalence of occult hepatitis B virus infection, knowledge and preventive practices against hepatitis B virus in barbers serving the armed forces," *J. Clin. Exp. Hepatol.*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 668-673, 2021.
9. H. C. Egbu, H. I. Mohammed, and G. R. Pennap, "Patterns of Hepatitis B Virus Infection Serologic Markers among Blood Donors at a Tertiary Healthcare Facility in Central Nigeria," *Int. Res. J. Gastroenterol. Hepatol.*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 28-36, 2020.
10. K. Patwa et al., "KGHeBTA (King George's medical university hepatitis B therapeutic algorithm): a new diagnostic and therapeutic algorithm and clinico-epidemiological spectrum of hepatitis B," *J. Clin. Exp. Hepatol.*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 629-637, 2023.
11. Katamba and O. O. Philippe, "Epidemiology of Hepatitis B Virus," in *Hepatitis B*, IntechOpen, 2021.
12. S. Sundaram, H. Darak, S. Kumar, S. Giri, and S. Bhatia, "DAPS score—a novel score for prediction of significant fibrosis in incidentally detected asymptomatic hepatitis B subjects," *Clin. Exp. Hepatol.*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 9-13, 2023.
13. B. Musunuri et al., "Profile of patients with hepatocellular carcinoma: An experience from a tertiary care center in India," *Indian J. Gastroenterol.*, vol. 41, no. 2, pp. 127-134, 2022.
14. Y. Musa, H. I. Isa Mohammed, and G. R. Rinmecit Pennap, "Distribution and Prevalence of Markers of Hepatitis B Virus Infection among HIV-Positive Patients attending Defence Healthcare Facility in Abuja, Nigeria," *AJRRHE*, 2022.
15. S. A. A. SICK, "Prevalence of Hepatitis B Surface Antigen and Hepatitis B Surface Antibody among Sick and Apparently Healthy Individuals in Osun State," Ph.D. dissertation, Dept. Microbiol., Obafemi Awolowo Univ., Ile-Ife, 2020.